

Covenant as a ‘Gift of Proximity’

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Abstract

This article aims to explore the biblical theme of covenant in its manifold subtleties. While conceiving a covenant both as an act of immediacy and mediacy of God towards his chosen people, it establishes the extraordinary disposition of God as a ‘Gift of proximity’ rather than a pact or treaty. To validate this stance, the author would briefly examine the different modalities of mediation (mediacy) present both in the Old and the New Testaments that are institutionalized as part and parcel of their socio-religious life. Having considered the different modalities of mediation, he would draw our attention to Eucharist and Ecclesia as intensified discourses of the New Covenant in the person of Jesus Christ.

Introduction

An interesting comment of Walter Brueggemann on the illustrious Michelangelo’s painting ‘The Creation of Adam’ emphasizes the two-fold complexity of God, i.e., God as immeasurably sovereign and as infinitely faithful. It points us towards the two-fold dynamics at play, i.e., the strange alterity as well as the extraordinary proximity of God. Our investigation proceeds exactly from this starting point. The concrete instances of testimonies or the audacious declarations of the patriarchs as well as the prophets regarding the various traces of immediacy (unmediated direct theophanies) and mediacy (mediated or indirect interventions) ranging all throughout the history of the chosen people manifest the extraordinary disposition and the deep-set concern of God in drawing the Covenant.

If we try to explore the different modalities of God’s mediation (mediacy) in the Old Testament, we could notice that there were mainly five in number. They are Torah, Kingship, Prophet, Cult and Wisdom. Each of these modalities of mediation was painstakingly instituted as a gift springing from God’s kind disposition towards his people. What we see in the Scripture is that all these five modalities of mediation were reverentially observed with greater reliability, i.e., even to the point of being considered as important institutions in their own socio-

religious setting. The modalities of mediation as structured institutions regularly disciplined Israel through instructive discourses. Thus, it marks the institutional as well as the instructive role of the mediations in the socio-religious setting of the faithful.

The new mediation or the disposition of God (Jer. 31, 31-34) in the person of Jesus Christ sums up and perfects all the five institutionalized mediations in its totality. While fulfilling the redemptive Will of the Father through the paschal mystery, the New Covenant gets effectively communicated in the form of concrete sacramental symbols of Eucharist and *Ecclēsia* (Church), as intensified discourses. Thus, an effective terrain for improving our intimate union with God, as well as the conditions to overcome our limited justice and religiosity, is prepared.

Covenant: Terms, Meanings and Clarification

A covenant is generally understood as a pact or agreement that is drawn between two willing parties who have made a contract among themselves to associate, consent, consolidate, and mutually avail the benefits. Oftentimes, an inherent utilitarian perspective – what could I benefit from this deal? – would be the latent driving force behind such contractual relationships. Such a reductive perspective blurs the deep intricacies of this notion. To comprehend this complex notion of the covenant in its manifold subtleties, it is quite indispensable to understand the different terms and their vivid range of meanings in some of the biblical languages. It would thus help us to arrive at that single term that clarifies and inclusively portrays the right theological sense of the word. In a way, it demands careful and cautious lexical or philological investigations.

The Hebrew word for covenant is *b^erit*. In the common parlance, it would mean covenant, pact, treaty, agreement, commitment, contract, accord, alliance, plot, and conspiracy. Whereas in the religious sense, it refers to that specific symbol of the relationship between man/woman/people and his/her/their God. The word *b^erit* which is derived from the noun *biri tu* literally means “obligation or bond” and metaphorically would mean “the binding covenant”. This special kind of bonding directs us towards the importance of relationality as initiated by God Himself, rather than considering it as a contractual pact between two equal parties. This disposition for proximity initiated by God Himself is indeed to be understood it as a Gift or as a special kind of invitation towards building a relationship centered on His unconditional love.

The Greek word that corresponds to the Hebrew word *b^erit* is *spondê*, which simply refers to the libation that takes place during the ceremonial conclusion of a

covenant. But for theological reasons, *b^erit* is translated in the LXX with the Greek word *diathêkê* which would mean disposition of the last will or testament. It is translated in this manner at a range of 267 instances out of the whole 287 occurrences. Another Greek word that has the same sense of *spondê* is *synthêkê*. The weighted preference to use *diathêkê* instead of *synthêkê* is for the following reason. While *synthêkê* focusses on the bilateral sense of the covenant (i.e., as drawn between two equal wills or parties), *diathêkê* would accentuate the unilateral sense and emphasizes the role of the higher will in establishing or initiating an order, as rightly implied in the meaning of *b^erit*. It would thus accommodate and resolve the problematic issues of incompatibility and asymmetry in the covenant (in so far as it is conceived as to be drawn between two unequal parties).

In our attempt to identify and clarify these inherent subtleties through a lexical or philological investigation, we have indeed succeeded in overcoming the reductive view, i.e., covenant being conceived either as a mere reciprocal contract or as a treaty between the suzerains and the vassals, where the feudalistic model of superimposition of sets of rules or laws over the subordinate group aimed at the purpose of exploitation is validated. We could conclude from these clarifications that covenant is not to be seen as a mere contract of reciprocity, but as a gift of proximity or as a creative act of God springing out of His unconditional love. Therefore, the complementary party is at a receiving or beneficial end and literally has no choice or control over God's disposition except to accept it as a gift or to outwardly deny and live in deprivation of the promised goodness.

Tracing the Immediacy and Mediacy of God in OT and NT

While tracing the Immediacy of God in the Old Testament, we could take into consideration the public Theophany at Mount Sinai (Ex. 19, 9-25 and its culmination in Ex. 24, 3-18) and some of the personal Theophanies or encounters (for e.g., the encounters of Abraham, Moses, and Elijah etc. with God). All these public and personal Theophanies or encounters comprise of a heavily shared communitarian goal and demand conformity, responsibility, and perfect reciprocity towards God's extended provisions. Whereas in the course of tracing the modalities of God's Mediacy (i.e., all His indirect mediations or interventions) in the Old Testament, we could mainly see them in five different forms like Torah, Kingship, Prophet, Cult, and Wisdom. Each of these modalities of mediation is instituted as a Gift, arising from God's extremely kind disposition towards His own chosen people.

The Torah (Law), as authorized by God was intended to protect His chosen people from all their inclinations towards multiple kinds of idolatries. It enabled a

sacred conscience so to tackle and purify them from all their wrongful discernments, distortive judgements, and perverted contempt in living out God's holiness and identity. It, in a way, effectively bound them to the love of God and to the love of neighbor. The live discourse of Torah helped them to endure and escape their own disintegration through awful ways of life.

The Kingship (Regality), as authorized by God was intended to enforce and ensure the right practice of the Torah (Deut. 17, 14-20). Thus, the kings of Israel were generally considered as authorized agents of God, ordained to fulfill His will on earth and to ensure the covenantal mode of community existence. The gift of kingship was also at times reluctantly made and that too with explicit restrictions. Since kingship was marked by God's purpose, self-aggrandizement was curbed (Deut. 17, 16-17) and God's righteousness was sought and lived out (Ps. 72:1-4,12- 14). The live discourse of Kingship safeguarded Israel from all its possible external attacks and schooled them in divine providence and protection.

Individual prophetic figures, as authorized by God were intended to attest to the mind of God and to intervene in the concrete life situations of the chosen people with a different message other than their own and that from above. Prophets arose in Israel when the covenantal mode of both the communitarian as well as the individual existence was in decay or under threat. And it has been the responsibility of the prophets to intervene and insist Israel mend their ways so as to live out God's will and purpose, and to enunciate the consequences of a life lived less in conformity to the covenantal exigency and love.

Worship, as authorized by God, enabled the chosen people with an adequate space and customized preferences to perform rites and rituals. It spatially ensured them of God's reassuring presence and rightly situated them in their performative drive to worship and adore. Israel received favors, forgiveness, and fruits of reconciliation through their frequency to worship. Israel expressed all their needs, stated all their grievances, and faithfully uttered the doxologies through meaningful rites and rituals. As a result of this specific performative religiosity of Israel, they indeed enjoyed genuine fellowship with God and thereby lived out their directedness through rites and rituals as lived moments of divine encounters.

Though scholars conventionally opine that the teachers of wisdom are only those who are capable of discernment and those who have a great deal of life experiences, the gift of wisdom should be rather understood in terms of a completely unique kind of in-built authorization and legitimation. Wisdom is to be recognized as a gift from God and it is to be attested with some glorified awareness of the covenantal bond. True discernment, therefore, is not merely a byproduct of

human intelligence, common sense, or even an outcome of experiences derived from the longevity and the maturity of a person, but it is a special kind of endowment or power from God or a gift from above bestowed without reserve or conditions. Israel was indeed schooled by the sapiential writings that in a way determined their moving closer to God and simultaneously helped them to be directed towards the covenantal living.

While tracing the Immediacy of God in the New Testament, we could notice that the very mystery of Incarnation itself marks to be the most perfect Theophany of all times. Likewise, while tracing the renewed disposition or the Mediacy of God (Jer. 31, 31-34) in the person of Jesus Christ, we could discover that He sums up, refines, and perfects all the five modes of mediations in their totality. Therefore, we could conclude that both the Immediacy and Mediacy of God blend in an incredibly mysterious way in the person of Jesus Christ and get effectively actualized through the sacramental symbols of Eucharist and *Ecclesia*. The covenantal continuum, in that way, could be seen as getting reinstated as well as reconfigured through Jesus' discourses, sermons, parables, healings, miracles, and more concretely through the words of institution. The conglomerating spectrum of this perfect blend institutionalizes Eucharist and *Ecclesia* as the sacramental symbols par excellence of covenantal love and displays them as effective means to conscientize as well as to contribute to the covenantal living of the chosen people.

Covenant as a Gift of Proximity: Eucharist and *Ecclesia*

The divine incarnation marks to be the most evident expression of God's gift of proximity. While considering the reassuring presence and proximity of God in the person of Jesus Christ, we could possibly figure out some concrete ways in which God grounded, enabled, and inaugurated the New Covenant. The authoritative formulaic words of Jesus not only prefigured and inaugurated the Kingdom of God but also instituted His Sacramental presence in the Holy Eucharist. His redemptive and willful death effectively provisioned the essential requisites for the covenantal bond.

The birth narratives of the Gospel and the prophecies related to it highlight an essential aspect of Jesus' proximity. It is fundamentally characterized as *Shekhina* or Immanuel or as 'God is with us' (Is. 7,14). Similarly, in the closing words of the final mandate for evangelization given by Jesus to His disciples, one could find the same feature present in the form of a solemn promise, that is "remember, I am with you always, to the end of the age." (Mt. 28.20). This promise of proximity in a way draws us close to a renewed and reconfigured kind of God's

disposition. It is also marked by a willingness of God to be present in the lives of the chosen ones, despite of their infidelity. This does not advocate a kind of unilateral engagement, rather signifies a qualified access to God's merciful disposition and unconditional love, as an open gift.

In the Old Testament, the conclusion of a covenant was always accompanied by an external sign, such as the erection of a monument (*stéle*) or a physical impairment inflicted to the body (circumcision) etc. Similarly, the New Covenant concluded by Jesus himself was also accompanied by an external sign. More than labelling it as a mere external sign, it could be identified as a sacramental symbol denoting the real presence of Jesus. It is nothing else than the Holy Eucharist itself. This efficacious sacramental symbol could be understood as a gift par excellence of the New Covenant, where God's kind disposition becomes tangible and comprehensible to the minds of the faithful and remains as a symbolic heritage for future generations.

H. B. Green, in his book *The Gospel According to Matthew*, explained the notion of the Church as the Body of Christ. Alberto Mello opined that Matthew was the only evangelist to use the term *Ecclesia* for church. Instead of recalling the normal Greek conception of *Ecclesia* (church) as a mere assembly of faithful, he tried to portray it as a place where Israelites gathered to draw a covenant. Here, the notion of *Ecclesia* embraces the implication of covenant. It refers both to the body of Christ and to the spatial coordinate where the assembly of faithful entered into a covenantal bond. While integrating both these views, i.e., the physical presence as well as the spatial significance, we could affirm the effectiveness and efficaciousness of both the sacramental symbols as authorized discourses to fully conscientize as well as to perfectly configure the chosen ones in the profound remembrance of God. The underlying feature of *Shekhina* gets reinstated by the integration of both these sacramental symbols of Eucharist and *Ecclesia*. Concomitantly, they also include the perfect interplay of the dual aspects of grace (in so far as they are sacramental in nature) and gift (in so far as they are unconditionally bestowed and not strived for).

Conclusion

While Covenant, in the common parlance, is conceived as a bilateral agreement, treaty, or pact that ensures adequate possibilities to associate and to avail mutual benefits between two or more willfully parties, the covenantal proceedings as envisaged in the theological parlance would imply an unconditional disposition of mercy that grounds, gifts, and grants. It enables a fuller growth in integrity and authenticity, without any amount of external exertion of power or force. Exploring

the pertinent theme of Covenant in its vivid subtleties, we have tried to understand and recognize the deep intricacies underlying the whole covenantal proceedings both in the Old and New Testaments within the keys of Immediacy and Mediacy of God. The Immediacy and Mediacy of God that regularly influenced, intervened, and instructed the chosen race did not determine their fate, rather emancipated and schooled them in virtues for a better covenantal living. The modalities of mediation played both an instructive as well as an institutional role, in so far as they were part and parcel of the socio-religious life of the chosen race. Towards the end of this article, we have found that in the person of Jesus Christ, we experience a perfect blend of both the immediacy and mediacy of God. Similarly, the covenantal continuum is also brought forth in the sacramental symbols of Eucharist and *Ecclesia*, in so far as they imbibe the perfect combination of grace and gratuity. Therefore, we conclude that covenant should not be understood as a mere mechanical arrangement of settling for, rather it needs to be conceived as a gift of proximity. This extraordinary gift of proximity doesn't scale and estimate our credits and worth in receiving it, rather disposes unconditionally and freely to enable us and to save us.

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